

and low total N (0.34%). Available P was 11-13 ppm (Olsen's method).

P rates did not affect the rice yields significantly (see table). In the second year, higher yields of transplanted rice were attributed to short and good

stand, synchronized ripening, lower sterility, and lower weed density.

The results showed that barley could follow transplanted rice. The yields of rice - barley were close to those of the main crops grown by local farmers. ☞

replications. The soil was medium black, fertilized with 25 kg N and 22 kg P/ha at sowing the last week of December and irrigated every 10-12 d with 50 mm of water at each of 10 irrigations.

Shulamith yielded significantly more dry pods than TG-1 and Kopargaon-1 (see table). SB-11 had the highest oil content. Spacing at 30 × 15 cm yielded significantly more dry pods. SB-11 at 30 × 15 cm produced the highest dry pod yield. ☞

High productivity varietal combinations in a rice - wheat rotation in Chhattisgarh, India

R. Singh, S.K. Shrivastava, S.N. Dubey, and B.R. Chandrawanshi, Zonal Agricultural Research Station (Rice Zone), Jawaharlal Nehru Krishi Vishwa Vidyalaya, Campus Raipur 492001, Madhya Pradesh, India

The Chhattisgarh area of Madhya Pradesh is a slightly moist hot zone with a moisture index between -20 and 0, and a mean annual temperature between 25° C and 18° C. Annual rainfall ranges from 1,000 to 1,500 mm, mostly concentrated in Jun-Sep. Soil type represents the red-yellow group, clay loam to clay. Rice, the principal crop, is grown mainly during the monsoon season, followed by linseed, lathyrus, urid, moong, gram, rape, mustard, and groundnut. Wheat is a recent second-crop introduction.

A 3-yr experiment to find the best varietal combination for high productivity in a rice - wheat rotation was initiated during 1978 kharif. Early, medium, and late duration rice varieties were followed by early, medium, and late duration wheat varieties in all combinations. Rice varieties were J.R.16-15-1-1 (90-100 d), Ratna (120-125 d), and Jaya (130-135 d). Wheat varieties were Sonalika (110 d), Jairaj (115 d), and K. Sona (125 d).

The experiment was a randomized block design with nine treatment combinations and four replications.

Effect of planting method on grain yield of 2 rice cultivars in Çorum, Turkey.^a

P rate (kg/ha)	Yield (t/ha)					
	Direct seeded			Transplanted		
	1983	1984	Mean	1983	1984	Mean
	<i>Ribe</i>					
0	7.2	3.2	5.2	5.5	4.5	5.0
18	7.4	2.8	5.1	5.5	3.8	4.6
35	6.9	3.2	5.1	5.5	4.3	4.9
53	7.3	3.2	5.3	6.0	4.3	5.2
Mean	7.2	3.1	5.2	5.6	4.2	4.9
	<i>Krasnodarsky 424</i>					
0	9.3	5.9	7.6	6.9	6.5	6.7
18	9.1	5.9	7.5	6.9	6.9	6.9
35	9.6	5.6	7.6	6.7	6.8	6.8
53	10.3	6.3	8.3	6.8	7.2	7.0
Mean	9.6	5.9	7.8	6.7	6.9	6.8

^aIn both planting methods and years: P rates - ns, CV (%) - 8.54 in 1983, 10.20 in 1984, P × cultivar - ns, CV (%) - 6.11 in 1983, 6.71 in 1984.

Irrigated peanut following rice in Konkan, India

S.T. Thorat and B.P. Patil, Konkan Agricultural University, Dapoli 415712, Maharashtra, India

In Konkan, a humid area with heavy monsoon rainfall (3,000-3,500 mm a year), rice has been a single Jun-Oct crop. Introduction of irrigation in the

dry season has created opportunities for double cropping.

We evaluated peanut varieties and optimal spacing. The legume oil seed crop has high market value in the area.

Combinations of five peanut varieties (TG-1, M-13, Shulamith, SB-11, and Kopargaon-1) with 115-120 d maturity and 3 spacings (30 × 15, 45 × 15, and 30 × 30 cm) were evaluated in a randomized block design with 3

Dry pod yield of peanut varieties and plant spacing.^a Konkan, India.

Variety	Dry pod yield (t/ha)			Mean yield (t/ha)	Oil (%)
	30 × 15 cm	45 × 15 cm	30 × 30 cm		
TG-1	2.7	2.9	2.7	2.8	47.8
M-13	3.1	2.9	2.8	2.9	48.3
Shulamith	3.4	3.3	2.5	3.1	46.2
SB-11	3.6	2.6	2.5	2.9	51.4
Kopargaon-1	2.4	2.5	2.4	2.4	48.8
Mean	3.1	2.8	2.6	-	-

CD at 5%

Variety	0.2
Spacing	0.2
Variety × Spacing	0.4

^a1978-80 pooled averages.